

DISTRIBUTED XiL TESTING METHODOLOGY

EM-TECH

Cost reduction through remote hardware testing

Enables real-time testing across multiple remote sites with diverse facilities and components

Enhance collaboration between R&D teams

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTION:

Testing innovative electric motors in the automotive sector using Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) enables safe, cost-effective, and realistic validation of new designs without a full physical prototype. By simulating the vehicle environment, engineers can evaluate performance, control strategies, and safety aspects efficiently. Within the EM-TECH project, a distributed XiL (X-in-the-Loop) setup connects the HiL facilities at TUIL and USR via a Virtual Private Network (VPN). This real-time link enables synchronized co-simulation of components located at different sites, supporting rapid control prototyping and system-level testing using a full vehicle model. For example, control solutions for the on-board powertrain are tested with the TRA motor running at USR while the vehicle simulator and controller operate at TUIL.

IMPACT AND NEXT STEPS:

The XiL environment enables advanced HiL testing that would otherwise be difficult to achieve. It enhances flexibility, scalability, and collaboration between research and development teams while reducing travel costs and improving overall efficiency. Moving forward, the distributed XiL setup will support the design and testing of integrated electric powertrains for next-generation mobility platforms.

Figure 1: XiL framework

The distributed XiL setup links USR and TUIL, with the AFM motor at USR providing torque to TUIL's virtual vehicle and brake HiL systems. A closed loop synchronizes real motor and brake tests with virtual simulation.

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